

5. Y. MIZUTANI, R. YAMANE, H. IHARA and H. MOTOMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1963, **36**, 361; 1965, **38**, 689.
6. A. S. BASU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 299.
7. S. K. SAHARAY and A. S. BASU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 370.
8. M. R. J. WYLLIE and S. L. KANAAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 73.
9. S. DRAY and K. SOLLNER, *Biochim. et. Biophys. Acta*, 1955, **18**, 341.
10. S. K. SAHARAY and A. S. BASU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 1120.
11. F. HELFFERICH, 'Ion Exchange', McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc. (New York), 1962, 378.

Constituents of *Aspergillus niger*

H. K. BHAT, G. N. QAZI, C. L. CHOPRA, K. L. DHAR*
and
C. K. ATAL

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu Tawi-180 001

Manuscript received 22 August 1978, revised 30 April 1979,
accepted 4 August 1979

ASPERGILLUS niger is a fungus commonly used in the commercial production of citric acid. The wet mycelium is obtained in large quantities after the recovery of citric acid. Since this mycelial mat, 1 kg dry wt. obtained for every 10 kg of citric acid produced, is at present going waste, it was thought worthwhile to study its chemical composition, with the objective of finding some useful byproducts.

The dried ground mycelium (4 kg) was extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in a soxhlet for 42 hrs. Chromatography of the extract over silica gel and rechromatography over alumina yielded three distinct fractions. Fraction "1" contained stearic acid, m.p. 70-71°, identified from spectroscopic data and formation of derivatives.

Fraction "2" yielded on crystallisation from methanol-benzene shining crystals, (0.3 g), m.p. 145-146°, showing positive test for sterols. Analytical data suggested its molecular formula to be $C_{28}H_{44}O$, confirmed by mass spectrum which showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 396, the other prominent peaks being at m/e 363, 337 and 271. Pmr⁺ showed signals at δ 0.64-1.16 (six methyls), 3.5 (1H, D₂O exchangeable, C3-OH), 5.22 (2H, broad multiplet, C22, 23-olefinic protons) and 5.5 (1H, multiplet, C15-H).

It gave a monoacetate, $C_{30}H_{46}O_2$, m.p. 148-149°, [α]_D -60° (CHCl₃), $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1240 cm⁻¹ (Acetate). Pmr showed a singlet at δ 2.01 (3H, -OCOCH₃). Oxidation

† All PMR spectra in this paper were measured in CCl₄ solution with TMS as internal standard in a 60 MHz instrument.

(Jones)⁸ of the sterol formed a 3-keto compound, m.p. 162°, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1717 cm⁻¹ (C=O stretching). On hydrogenation (Pd/C, 5%) the sterol absorbed 2 moles of hydrogen forming the tetrahydro derivative, m.p. 152°, which when further subjected to hydrogenation (Pd/C, acetic acid) absorbed one more mole of hydrogen to yield the hexahydro derivative, thus showing that there are three double bonds and that one of the double bonds is tetra substituted.

The above physico-chemical evidences suggested the compound to be 24-methyl-5 β -cholesta-8, 14, 22-trien-3 β -ol(I) (lit⁹, m.p. 144-5°), confirmed by m.m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

Fraction "3" furnished a white crystalline solid (0.2 g) m.p. 178°. It also showed positive test for sterols. Analytical data suggested its molecular formula to be $C_{28}H_{44}O_3$, confirmed by mass spectrometry which showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 428, the other peaks being at 410, 396, 392 and 376 mass units. Pmr shows signals at δ 6.38 (2H, AB quartet, J=6Hz, 6H & 7-H), 5.25 (2H, broad multiplet, 22-H & 23-H), 3.9 (1H, D₂O exchangeable, 3-OH) and 0.93 to 1.4 (six methyls).

The above data indicated its identity with ergosterol peroxide(II)^{11,14}, confirmed by comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc) with an authentic sample and by the formation of its acetate, m.p. 202-203°, [α]_D -23° (CHCl₃).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. R. K. Thapa, Dr. S. K. Chaturvedi and Mr. S. Kaul for their valuable suggestions. We are also thankful to Miss. B. P. Jalali and Dr. Dinesh for the spectral data and M/s CIBA Laboratories and Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat for supplying the mass data. One of the authors (HKB) is thankful to CSIR for the award of JRF.

References

1. P. WIELAND and V. PRELOG, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, **30**, 1028.
2. M. FISHER, W. E. ROSEN and L. F. FISHER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5897.

3. A. W. D. HUDGELL, J. H. TURNBULL and W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 814.
4. G. BAUSLAUGH, G. JUST and F. BLANK, *Nature*, 1964, **202**, 1218.
5. T. L. HO, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1972, No. 20, 807.

Chemical Constituents of *Vallisneria spiralis*

O. Ktze

R. L. KHOSA, A. K. WAHI and A. K. MUKHERJEE

Department of Pharmaceutics, Institute of Technology,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 24 April 1978, revised 2 January 1979,
accepted 4 August 1979

THE latex obtained from *Vallisneria spiralis* O. Ktze (Apocyanaceae) is widely used as an anti-inflammatory agent in the treatment of old wounds and sores¹. Some phytochemical work on this plant is on record^{2,3,4}. The present note reports the isolation of some chemical constituents from its leaves.

The powdered airdried leaves of *V. spiralis* were extracted successively with petroleum ether and benzene in a Soxhlet. The petrol extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina and the benzene eluates upon concentration and cooling yielded a crystalline sterol m.p. 134-35°; acetate m.p. 126-28°; benzoate m.p. 141-43°. It was identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p. and IR) of the compound and its derivatives with the authentic samples.

The benzene extract on concentration and cooling separated a crystalline mass identified as potassium nitrate. The concentrated mass was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina and the petrol-benzene (10:2) eluates yielded a triterpene alcohol which crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 187-89°; IR (nujol) broad band between 3300-3400 cm^{-1} (-OH); acetate, m.p. 238-39° and benzoate m.p. 229-31°, suggesting its identity with β -amyrin which was further confirmed by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., co-TLC and IR) with authentic samples. The chloroform-methanol (1:6) eluates furnished a triterpene acid, m.p. 277-79°; IR (KBr) 3350-3450 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1685 cm^{-1} (C=O) and other peaks at 1380, 1370, 1350, 1305, 1270 and 1247 cm^{-1} characteristic of ursolic acid derivatives⁵. The mass spectrum showed besides molecular ion peak M^+ at m/e 456, prominent fragment ions at m/e 538(5%), 410(8%), 248(100%), 203(53%) and 133(53%) suggesting the compound to be ursolic acid. NMR (CDCl_3) exhibited signals for C-12 olefinic proton at δ 5.2, polymethylene envelope between δ 1.2-2.0 and seven methyl groups as singlets between δ 0.66-1.01. The compound formed a methyl ester, m.p. 169-70°. Finally, the identity of the compound with ursolic acid was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. A. B. Ray, Dept. of Medicinal Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University for the authentic samples.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R, New Delhi, 1956, p 252.
2. K. W. GOPINATH, P. A. MOHAMED and A. R. KIDWAI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 98.
3. H. KAUFMANN, W. WEHRLI and T. REICHSTEIN, *Helv. Chem. Acta.*, 1965, **48**, 65.
4. M. N. VOHRA, G. K. PATNAIK, R. S. KAPIL and N. ANAND, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1966, **55**, 1425.
5. K. YAMAGUCHI, "Spectral data of Natural Products", Elsevier Publishing Company, London, 1970, Vol 1, p. 132.

Possible Antibacterial Compounds.

Synthesis of Alkyl penta-trans-2, trans-4 dienoic and Alkyl propyl-trans-2-enoic Acid Amides

BALDEV VIG, RAM KANWAR and SATVIR SINGH

DAHIYA

Department of Chemistry, Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak

Manuscript received 29 August 1978, revised 28 February
1979, accepted 4 August 1979

VARIOUS types of acid amide have been shown to be physiological active substances. Conjugated alkyl amides show significant insecticidal activity towards housefly¹. Many substituted toluamides have been shown to have antibacterial and insect repellent properties^{2,3}. In view of this it was thought of interest to synthesise various unsaturated alkyl amides.

The key reaction employed for the synthesis of various alkyl amides was modified Wittig reaction. Aliphatic aldehyde was submitted to modified Wittig reaction with γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate or α -phosphonate of ethyl acetate to get the unsaturated esters. It has been shown that Wittig reaction of ylid enjoying resonance stabilization tend to be stereospecific and yield a great preponderance of trans product^{4,5}. This has been further proved to be so by spectral data of synthetic products. Various aldehydes such as heptaldehyde, palmitic aldehyde, citronellal and citral were used as starting material for the projected synthesis of various acid amide I to V. Typical procedure for the unsaturated acid amide was as follows.

Heptaldehyde was condensed with γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate in the presence of NaH using